

THE IMPACT OF FOOD PROCESSING INNOVATIONS ON CONSUMER PERCEPTION OF FOOD SERVED BY INFORMAL FOOD-SERVICE OPERATORS: A PERSPECTIVE OF SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA

Adedeji T. Funke^{1*} and Oladeji David²

¹*African Institute for Science Policy and Innovation, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife,
Nigeria*

²*Department of Consumer Science and Family Nutrition, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife,
Nigeria*

*Corresponding author email: tfadedeji@oauife.edu.ng

Abstract

This paper explores how innovations in food processing influence consumer perceptions in the informal foodservice sector of Oyo State, Nigeria. A mixed-method approach was employed, utilizing structured questionnaires and observational checklists to gather data from 60 consumers and 180 informal foodservice operators (IFOs) across six local government areas. The data indicates that 71.2% of the operators have embraced innovations like electric blenders and gas cookers, leading to enhanced efficiency and hygiene in meal preparation. Consumer ratings reflect a high level of satisfaction with food quality, especially in terms of taste, aroma, and appearance. However, there are ongoing concerns about water quality and environmental cleanliness. Obstacles to innovation faced by the remaining operators consist of restricted technical expertise and financial limitations. The investigation highlights the promise of affordable technological solutions to improve food quality in informal environments, while stressing the importance of supportive policies, training, and regulatory oversight. The results provide important information for decision-makers seeking to enhance food safety and service quality within Nigeria's informal food sector.

Keywords: *Innovation, Consumers, Food wholesomeness, Informal Foodservice Operators*

1.0 Introduction

Food is described as any substance and/or product that can be eaten or drunk by people and/or animals (Aceves *et al.*, 2022). It is required to maintain and increase the standard of living or it is used as a nutrition or medical supplement (Savov and Kouzmanov, 2009; Zheng *et al.*, 2022). The changes in world demography have led to an estimate of about 2.5 billion people all over the world consuming food out of home on a daily basis, which may be because they find it cheap or convenient (Fellows and Hilmi, 2018; Omotayo and Denloye, 2019). Akanji *et al.* (2015) stated that 95% of working-class Nigerians in urban settings eat outside their homes and are, therefore, vulnerable to hazards attributed to poor quality meals. This could affect the achievement of the third Sustainable Developments Goals (SDG) 2030, and lead to lack of economic growth if not properly managed.

There are over two million reported cases of food poisoning annually throughout the world with estimated deaths of two hundred thousand people in Nigeria alone, which include young children

(Ezirigwe 2018; Usman and Modupe, 2021). According to Adewole and Adepoju (2019), Nigeria has only given priority to food security and neglected food quality in years past. A World Bank report also showed that Nigeria and other developing countries lose about \$10B annually due to low productivity and in the treatment of illnesses arising from low quality food. The report further stated that this can be solved through direct incorporation and adoption of preventive measures on how to improve food processing procedures from farm to mouth (WHO, 2006).

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has adopted the Five Keys to Safer Food, which are: Keep clean, separate raw and cooked foodstuffs, cook thoroughly, keep food at safe temperatures and use safe water and raw materials. These keys can be integrated into the foodservice operation system through the use of technology. This will enhance the ability of the informal food service operators IFOs to produce wholesome food to the community in which they operate.

After the rapid development of many economies, quality standards, imposed on the food industry, are getting much more focused on consumers' rising and persistent demand for safe food and better quality food and beverage. Consumers' expectations and perceptions (taste, aroma, freshness, and appearance) are assuming higher dimensions daily (Savov and Kouzmanov, 2009; Zheng *et al.*, 2022). The quality of the products sold is one of the most important elements for every business that offers goods and services. The quality concept within the food service industry puts importance on three key factors namely:

1. intended purpose of product conformity;
2. product safety; and
3. consumers' expectations and perceptions (Faroutan *et al.*, 2022).

Throughout the world, food-borne diseases caused an estimated 600 million infections and 420,000 premature deaths in 2019 (Fontannaz-Aujoulat and Schlundt, 2019). In developing countries, the total productivity loss associated with food-borne diseases is estimated at \$95.2bn per year, and the annual cost of treating food-borne diseases is estimated at \$15bn (Stiglitz, 2018; Gargiulo, 2022). This calls for proper safety and sanitation in food management (Adewole and Adepoju, 2019). The situation is exacerbated by people's ignorance of food hygiene, lack of government coordination of food safety control methods, and poor enforcement of food safety regulations (Omojokun, 2013). This then raises the question, despite several evolving innovations on food processing has it really impacted the food quality, sensory evaluation and consumer perception? The informal foodservice sector is essential for delivering affordable meals and creating job opportunities, especially in fast-growing urban areas such as Nigeria. With the evolution of consumer expectations, the convergence of innovations in food processing and the perception of food quality has garnered heightened academic interest (Yan, Hsieh, & Ricacho, 2022). The way consumers perceive food quality is significantly shaped by sensory attributes such as taste, aroma, and appearance, in addition to observable hygiene standards and the quality of service provided. Röhl *et al.* (2024) observe that consumers typically favour minimally processed foods, viewing them as more natural and healthier options. In casual dining settings with minimal supervision, such beliefs significantly affect what consumers choose and how satisfied they feel. Liu *et al.* (2022) highlights that the visual presentation and sensory appeal of food hold equal importance to its intrinsic nutritional value.

Technological advancements in informal food operations—like the implementation of electric blenders, gas cookers, and improved packaging—have demonstrated a positive impact on the efficiency of meal preparation and the satisfaction of customers (Afzali & Ahmed, 2016). Nonetheless, the availability of these technologies is not consistent across different regions. A

study by Adepoju, Adewole, and Akinkuolie (2022) emphasizes that financial limitations, insufficient training, and infrastructural obstacles persist in obstructing the broad implementation of innovative practices among food vendors in Nigeria.

Ilori, Oke, and Sanni (2000) emphasize that advancements in food service, especially in terms of process innovation, are influenced not just by the availability of technology but also by the capabilities of the organization and its orientation towards the market. Marketing innovation and adaptations in business models significantly impact consumer perceptions of service quality and food reliability (Foroutan, Bouzari, & Safavi, 2022). Moreover, the issue of food safety continues to be of paramount importance. Gargiulo *et al.* (2022) and Omotayo and Denloye (2019) highlight that the risks associated with food-borne illnesses as shown in Plate 1 below, are heightened in informal environments where regulatory enforcement is lacking, underscoring the critical need for the implementation of safe processing methods.

Plate 1: Different causes of food contamination

Source: FAO (2007)

The first commercial application of a new technology in the form of a product, process, or service is referred to as technological innovation. Depending on the form of technology, it occurs as a result of a series of events that span a long period of time. Concept creation, idea screening, research and development, business analysis, product growth, test marketing, and commercialization are some of their responsibilities (Ilori *et al.*; 2000; Ilori, 2006). These seven stages are divided into three categories: pure science, technology development and manufacturing, and marketing (Pires and Stanton, 2000).

Thus, the study aims to investigate the relationship between food process innovations and consumer perception of quality among the IFOs. It focuses on the informal food service system, which continues to evolve in response to the needs of a substantial percentage of the consumer population. To ensure that food served to consumers are wholesome, a strong national food safety policy is needed (Omotayo and Denloye, 2002; Enebele *et al.*, 2020).

2.0 Methodology

Stratified sampling technique and purposive sampling method were used to select six local government areas with urban and rural areas. Purposive sampling method was used to select the respondents that were administered questionnaires. A consumer each found at the site of ten randomly selected informal foodservice operators (IFOs) either stationary or semi mobile was selected across the six LGA making a total of 60 respondents (consumers) that were administered questionnaire to elicit information about their sensory evaluation and perception on the quality of the food they were consuming. This is made up of two sections namely socio-economic characteristics, experience, and their assessment of the quality of meals served. Activities of the consumers of the stationary IFOs contain both closed and open-ended questions (see Appendix I and II). Thirty IFOs spread in different locations like motor parks, market places, street junctions across six LGAs in Oyo State making a total of 180 respondents.

Consumer's Perception on Quality

A customer each from the selected IFO was asked questions on their perception of the quality of meals and drinks served at the time of conducting the survey and food samples were subjected to consumer sensory test using the method of Ikujeola (2010). The food samples, served fresh and hot, and the drinks being consumed at the time of the survey were compared with the food they had been consuming over time at informal foodservice spots. The consumers were not trained panelists but were given instruction to answer the question raised in terms of quality measurement as shown in Table 1. Each consumer was asked to rate their meal twice for appearance, colour, mouth feel, taste, aroma and overall acceptability using a 5 point hedonic scale, where 1 was disliked very much and 5 was liked very much. The instrument was subjected to reliability statistics to calculate the Cronbach α factor. The α factor was 0.7, meaning the instrument was reliable.

Table 1: Five-point Hedonic rating scale

Scale	Range	Description
5	4.5-5.0	Excellent
4	3.5-4.49	Very good
3	2.5-3.49	Good
2	1.5-2.49	Fairly good
1	1.0-1.49	Bad

Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data were expressed as means and Standard Deviation (SD) of at least three measurements. Each experimental set was compared with a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) procedure using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Duncan's new multiple range test was used to separate means. P values <0.05 were regarded as significant. The descriptive statistics employed the use of a univariate level of analysis in which the frequency counts of each of the variables (both explanatory and response variables as well as intervening variables) was examined in the presentation of the data.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Innovations found amongst the IFOs in the last five years

Table 2 below shows the innovation that was found amongst the IFOs in the last five years which indicates that 71.2% of the IFOs introduced new methods of meal preparation. For example, a broom was used for the preparation of *ewedu*, now a blender is being used; this makes it neater and faster to prepare. Electric motor grinders were used to mill boiled yam in pounded yam preparation, while mortar and pestle were used in the past. Gas cookers have replaced the use of firewood to save cost and energy. This indicates that the IFO surveyed sought better ways of preparing their meals through the use of new technology; this has eased their work and also made their service faster. The remaining 28.4% had not introduced a new method of meal preparation in the last five years. This may be due to lack of know-how, electricity supply and inadequate funding to invest in the purchase of new technology (Adedeji *et al.*, 2024).

Consumers' perception on quality

The mean rating by the consumers surveyed at the IFOs location at the time of the survey in the study area was 3.5 (Table 3). This showed that the consumers were satisfied with the sensory and quality of the meals served. The result indicated that consumers were satisfied with the taste (3.4), aroma (3.5), appearance (3.4), and presentation (3.4) of the food prepared and served by the IFOs in the study area. The results suggest that about 73 % of the consumers were satisfied with the quality of service rendered and the remaining 27 % wanted a better service.

Table 4 shows the number and type of meals consumed at the time the survey was carried out. This suggests that 47.0% of the consumers were consuming reconstituted dough (RD) like *amala*, *eba* and so on, while 39.2 %, 13.7 % were consuming grains and pasta at the time of the survey. The higher percentage that consume RD were mainly from the stationary operators because they had a place where consumers could be served comfortably.

The consumer that drank bottled water (19 %), sachet water (60 %) and other kind of drinks (21%), which includes non-alcoholic beverages, indicating that majority of the consumer drank sachet water probably because it was affordable as the consumers could only spend less than \$1.0 on a meal per day as shown in Table 5 below. The quality of the water served to consumers of the IFOs were rated as taste (2.7), odour (2.6), colour (2.7), and presentation (2.6). This implies that all the quality attributes of the water served to the consumers at the time of the survey were rated good.

Table 2: Innovations found amongst the IFOs in the last five years

		Stationary	Semi-mobile	Mobile	Total
Type of innovation		N-53(%)	N-65 (%)	N-51(%)	N-169(%)
Introduction of new method of meal preparation	Yes	40(75)	47(72)	34(66.7)	121(71.2)
	No	13(25)	18(28)	17(33.3)	48(28.4)
Development of new process	Yes	16(30.3)	14(21.5)	33(64.7)	48(28.4)
	No	37(69.8)	51(78.5)	18(35.3)	121(71.2)
Acquisition of new technology	Yes	35(66.1)	36(55.3)	26(50.9)	97(57.4)
	No	18(33.9)	29(44.6)	25(38.5)	72(42.6)
Organizational innovation	Yes	29(54.7)	36(56.0)	36(70.5)	101(59.7)
	No	24(45.2)	29(44.6)	15(29.4)	68(40.2)
Marketing innovation	Yes	23(43.3)	21(32.3)	24(47.1)	68(40.2)
	No	20(37.7)	44(67.7)	27(52.9)	101(59.7)

Table 3: Quality rating of meal served by the Consumers

Ratings	5	4	3	2	1	Mean (3.5)
Taste	1(1.9)	9(16.7)	22(40.7)	10(18.5)	12(22.2)	3.4
Odour	2(3.7)	3(5.6)	25(46.3)	14(25.9)	10(18.5)	3.5
Appearance	1(1.9)	6(11.1)	27(50.0)	9(16.7)	11(20.4)	3.4
Presentation	3(5.6)	3(5.6)	28(51.9)	7(13.0)	13(24.1)	3.4

1- Bad; 2- Fairly good; 3 – Good; 4 – Very good; 5 – Excellent

Source: Author's survey 2022

Table 4: Types of Food being consumed

Category of food sold	Category of Operator		Total	%
	Semi-mobile	Stationary		
Reconstituted Dough (RD)	10	14	24	45.2
Grains	12	7	19	35.8
Pasta	5	2	7	13.2
Total	29	24	53	100

Reconstituted dough (RD) includes Amala, Eba, Semovita, Lafun, Pounded yam, and Fufu; Stew served with ewedu, okra, egusi, vegetable, and ogbono; Grains includes rice, beans and boiled maize; Pasta includes spaghetti, Indomie and Macaroni.

Source: Author's Survey (2022)

Table 5: Quality rating of water served with meal to the Consumers

Ratings	Excellent	Very good	Good	Fairly good	Bad	Mean	Mean of means
Overall	2(3.7)	3(5.6)	29(53.7)	10(18.5)	10(18.5)	2.41	
Taste	3(5.6)	9(16.7)	20(37.0)	12(22.2)	10(18.5)	2.7	
Aroma	2(3.7)	3(5.6)	30(55.6)	9(16.7)	10(18.5)	2.6	2.6
Appearance	3(5.6)	3(5.6)	31(57.4)	6(11.1)	11(20.4)	2.7	
Presentation	4(7.4)	6(11.1)	19(35.2)	13(24.1)	12(22.2)	2.6	

1- Bad; 2 – Fairly Good; 3 – Good; 4 – Very Good; 5 – Excellent

Source: Author's survey 2022

In order to have a good understanding of the perception of the consumers in relation to the quality of food being served by the IFOs, it was considered very important to explore the perception of their consumers towards the general cleanliness. This was done through a personal observational checklist and the results are shown in Table 6 below. The condition of the environment where the IFO operated was important in the delivery of quality meals; a dirty environment could lead to the production of unwholesome meals being served. Therefore, the general cleanliness of an environment was a positive indicator of quality of the food produced. The plates (Plates 2 and 3) showed that meals were produced on tiled floors using a gas cooker, as opposed to when meals were produced in a dusty environment using firewood. This implied that the informal IFOs had good knowledge, practice and attributes to produce wholesome food, as supported by the report of Omemu, (2008); Osagbemi *et al.*, (2010); Madubueze *et al.*, (2017); Iwu *et al.*, 2017; and Afzali and Ahmed, 2016). From Table 5, the location (the community where foodservice operated) of the foodservice operator seemed to be averagely clean as reported by the mean of 3.38. The environment, cooking area, and serving area were also averagely clean. The person serving the food exhibited a high degree of cleanliness, the same was applicable to the utensils used in meal presentation.

Table 6: General Cleanliness of the IFO operation site through observation

	1	2	3	4	5	TS	Mean (3.27)
Location (community where food service operates)							
	8(4.7)	19(11.2)	73(43.2)	38(22.5)	31(18.3)	572	3.38
Environment (place of operation)							
	17(10.1)	33(19.5)	51(30.2)	34(20.1)	34(20.1)	542	3.2
Cooking area	24(14.2)	35(20.7)	41(24.3)	43(25.4)	26(15.4)	519	3.07
Serving area	2(1.2)	11(6.5)	84(49.7)	54(32.0)	18(10.7)	582	3.44

5= Very Clean; 4=Clean; 3= Somewhat Clean; 2= Not Clean; 1= Very Dirty; MS = Mean Score; TS = Total Score

Source: Author’s survey (2022)

Preparation

Plate 2: The cooking areas where gas cooker and firewood were being used

Source: Author's survey (2022)

Plate 3: Serving areas from two different operation sites

Source: Author's survey (2022)

4.0 Conclusion

This study emphasizes the considerable impact of food processing innovations on how consumers perceive food quality in the informal foodservice sector in Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings indicate that a significant proportion of informal food operators (71.2%) have embraced new food preparation methods, including the utilization of electric blenders and gas cookers. These advancements not only boost the efficiency of meal preparation but also elevate the hygiene and overall attractiveness of the food offered. Consumers expressed overall satisfaction with the essential sensory characteristics—taste, aroma, and appearance—of meals offered by these operators, suggesting a favourable response to the innovations. Nonetheless, significant

deficiencies persist: approximately 28% of the operators were yet to adopt any type of innovation. This was easily attributed to limitations in resources and insufficient technical expertise. Moreover, factors like water quality, marketing innovation, and environmental cleanliness—despite demonstrating some advancement—continued to necessitate significant enhancement to align with anticipated public health and consumer service benchmarks.

The implications of these findings are twofold. Initially, they emphasize the significance of affordable technological advancements in improving food quality and safety within informal environments. Secondly, they highlight the critical necessity for supportive policies, financial access, training, and regulatory enforcement that could facilitate the wider implementation of best practices among informal food operators.

In summary, the incorporation of advancements in food processing is starting to reshape consumer experiences and enhance service quality. However, sustainable advancement will rely on a collaborative approach among various stakeholders—government bodies, non-governmental organizations, and educational institutions—to provide informal food operators with the essential tools, knowledge, and incentives needed to consistently offer safe and high-quality food. Future studies should investigate the lasting effects of these innovations on public health and economic results within Nigeria's informal food economy.

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*4th African Institute for Science Policy and Innovation Biennial International Conference
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APPENDIX I: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CONSUMERS

AFRICAN INSTITUTE FOR SCIENCE POLICY AND INNOVATION OBAFEMI
AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY, ILE IFE NIGERIA

QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY FOR THE STUDY ON INNOVATIONS IN FOOD
PROCESSING: ITS CONSEQUENCE ON SENSORY EVALUATION, FOOD QUALITY AND
CONSUMER PERCEPTION OF FOOD SOLD IN SOME LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN OYO
STATE, NIGERIA

Dear Sir/Ma,

This questionnaire is aimed at obtaining relevant information on the study of the level of technological capability in the informal foodservice industry in Oyo State. The survey is part of the Ph.D. programme and it is for research purposes. Please tick (✓) in the appropriate boxes or fill the space provided herein. All information shall be treated with utmost confidentiality. It will be appropriate if the information provided is as accurate as possible.

Thanks for your anticipated cooperation.

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

INTRODUCTION. Please, tick (✓) the appropriate answers in the following questions.

1. Gender. (a) Male (b) Female
2. Age (in years as at last birthday)
 - (a) Below 15 years
 - (b) Between 15 and 30 years
 - (c) Between 31 and 40 years
 - (d) Between 41 and 50 years
 - (e) Between 51 and 60 years
 - (f) Above 60 years
3. Marital Status
 - (a) Single
 - (b) Married
 - (c) Divorced
 - (d) Separated
 - (e) Widow
4. Highest Educational Qualification
 - (a) No formal education
 - (b) Primary School Education
 - (c) Modern School Education
 - (d) College/Secondary Education
 - (e) OND/NCE/HND/B.A./B.Ed./B/Sc/
 - (f) M.A/M.Ed/M.Sc/Ph.D.
5. Occupation
 - (a) Civil servant
 - (b) Trader
 - (c) Artisan

- (d) Student
- 6. What is your average monthly income?
 - (a) Below N20,000
 - (b) Between N20,000 and N50,000
 - (c) Between N50,000 and N100,000
 - (d) Above N100,000
- 7. Average of how much do you spend on a meal daily?
 - (a) Below N200
 - (b) Between N200 and N500
 - (c) Above N500
- 8. How frequent do you patronize here for food consumption?
 - (a) Very Often
 - (b) Often
 - (c) Rarely

SECTION B: CONSUMERS PERCEPTION OF QUALITY

- 1. How will you rate the premises of the food canteen?
(a)Excellent (b)very good (c)fairly good (d)bad (e)very bad
- 2. How will you rate their services?
(a)Excellent (b)very good (c) fairly good (d)bad (e)very bad
- 3. What meal are you consuming now?
(a)Reconstituted dough (RD) and stew b) Grain and stew c) Pasta and stew
- 4. Rate the quality of the meal you are consuming now in terms of the following scale

Five-point hedonic rating scale

Scale	Range	Description
1	4.5-5.0	Bad
2	3.5-4.49	fairly good
3	2.5-3.49	Good
4	1.5-2.49	very good
5	1.0-1.49	Excellent

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- (a) Taste 1 2 3 4 5
- (b) Aroma 1 2 3 4 5
- (c) Appearance 1 2 3 4 5
- (d) Overall
acceptability 1 2 3 4 5

5. What type of drink are you consuming now

- a) Sachet water b) Bottled water c) Other drinks e,g non- alcoholic beverages d) Both

6. What is the quality of the water served in terms?

- a) Taste Excellent, very good, fairly good, bad, very bad
b) Odour Excellent, very good, fairly good, bad, very bad
c) Appearance Excellent, very good, fairly good, bad, very bad
d) Presentation Excellent, very good, fairly good, bad, very bad

7. Please rate the level of improvement of quality of meal served overtime?

- (a)Very great (b)great (c)slight improvement (d)no improvement

8. Have you experienced any food poisoning case that can be traced to this food operator?

Yes/ No

If yes, how many times? (a)Once (b)Twice (c)Thrice

SECTION C-INNOVATIONS AND INNOVATION CAPABILITY AMONGST IFOs

Over the last 5 years, did your business introduce any new or upgraded products?

Definition. A new or upgraded product means the creation or adoption of new food or drink you serve to consumers. It also encompasses changes to the dining environment or marketing style where the customer consumes your product offerings.

2. Please rate the following factors in investment capacity as it concerns your outlet, on the following scale as 1. - Nil 2 – Low 3 - Fairly high 4 - High 5 - Very high

Innovation capability	1	2	3	4	5
(i) Ability to use of new technology					
(ii) Ability to introduce new menu					
(iii) Ability to introduce new method of meal preparation or preservation					
(iv) Ability to reorganize the whole process					
(v) Ability to changes an entire dining environment					

3. The innovations available for informal foodservice operators

S/N	Innovation	Number of Innovation
(a)	Product e.g change in meals served	
(b)	Process e.g change in production method	
(c)	Organisational e.g change in procedure of business	
(d)	Market e.g promotional activities	

APPENDIX II: OBSERVATIONAL CHECKLIST

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- 1. Local government area:
- 2. Location:
- 3. General cleanliness

5= Very Clean; 4=Clean; 3= Somewhat Clean; 2= Not Clean; 1= Very Dirty

S/N	General Cleanliness	1	2	3	4	5
1.	Location (community where foodservice operates)					
2.	Environment (place of operation)					
3.	Cooking area					
4.	Serving area					
5.	Operator cooking the meal					
6.	Utensils used in meal preparation					
7.	Person serving the meal					

- 4. Indicate other activities around the area where meals are being prepared.

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5. Indicate any form of innovation in their activities.

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6. General comment on the basis of your observation

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7. Indicate other activities around the area where meals are being prepared

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